

WAYS TO INCREASE THE SERVICE LIFE OF STAMP SURFACES AND HOW TO CHOOSE THE MOST OPTIMAL OPTION AMONG THEM

Shuhrat Fayzimatov, Bannobjon Rustamov
Fergana Polytechnic Institute,

Abstract. In this article, a scientific study was conducted on the selection of the most optimal chemical method among the methods of increasing the service life of stamps.

Key words: cementation , hardness , strength , heat resistance , requirements, surface purity , comparison , galvanic layer.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11079899>

Introduction

Different forms of chemical processing are common in industry. These are carburizing, nitriding, nitrocarburizing and cyanidation, as well as diffusion chroming, alitizing, boring, etc.[1]

The listed methods give special properties to the surface layer, therefore, depending on the conditions of the processed parts, it is necessary to choose the one that gives the desired property of the surface layer, depending on the grades of steel and fluid. We analyze the main methods of chemical processing that are widely used in industrial production conditions .[2]

There are types of cementing with solid, liquid and gas carburetors. Cementing in a liquid carburetor is universal and technically the simplest. The parts are placed in a box with a carburetor and placed in the stove for heating. The rate of carbonization on the basis of pistachio coal in a solid carburetor increases if 5...20% nitrate-cementite is added to its composition. The increase in the rate of cementation is explained by the interaction of nitrate-cementite with pistachio coal at the saturation temperature, in which a more effective gaseous compound is formed, which accelerates carbon diffusion to the metal surface.[4]

To increase the service life of metal products, it is necessary to increase its hardness, strength and heat resistance. Improvement of such properties is usually carried out by applying one of the thermal or chemical-thermal treatment methods.

Method

Stamp surfaces are under constant impact and friction. That's why, after studying and analyzing methods of increasing the service life of stamp surfaces, requirements are set for the result obtained from the processing method in order to choose the most optimal one.

Aspects to be studied: HB – hardness, R_a – surface cleanliness, σ_0 – durability.

Considered methods: U_N – nitriding, U_C – cementite coating, U_{Cr} – chroming, U_{Co} – . Cementation .

The properties achieved by each method are defined.

Nitriding

$$U_N (HB, R_a, \sigma_0) = \begin{cases} HB = 700 \\ R_a = 1,6 \text{ mkm} \\ \sigma_0 = 800 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Cobalt coating

$$U_C (HB, R_a, \sigma_0) = \begin{cases} HB = 560 \\ R_a = 1,6 \text{ mkm} \\ \sigma_0 = 900 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Chrome coating

$$U_{Cr}(HB, R_a, \sigma_0) = \begin{cases} HB = 1000 \\ R_a = 1,25 \mu\text{m} \\ \sigma_0 = 1100 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Cementation

$$U_{Co}(HB, R_a, \sigma_0) = \begin{cases} HB = 950 \\ R_a = 1,25 \mu\text{m} \\ \sigma_0 = 925 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Required properties

$$U_T(HB, R_a, \sigma_0) = \begin{cases} HB = 950 \\ R_a = 1,25 \mu\text{m} \\ \sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ MPa} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

By comparing the melting properties with the required properties, the most suitable method is selected. In this case, the significance of the properties being studied k is included in the coefficient comparison formula. In order to explain the importance, taking into account the working environment of the stamp dies, $k = 1$ we introduce the coefficients of hardness, strength ($k = 1$), surface cleanliness as important properties. $k = 0,5$

Compare:

Table 1.

No	Naming	Hardness HB	Surface cleanliness $R_a \mu\text{m}$	Strength σ_0 MPa
1	Required	1000	1.25	1000
2	Nitriding	700	1.6	800
3	Cobalt to cover	560	1.6	900
4	Chrome plating	1100	1.25	1000
5	Cementation	950	1.25	925
6	Significance	1	0.5	1

Figure 1. Choosing the most suitable coating method (surface cleanliness is calculated at $500/R_a$).

We carry out comparisons taking into account the importance. In this case, the degree of applicability is calculated by taking into account the importance of each compared property and is determined by dividing by the number of all studied properties.

Results

A comparison based on significance.

Nitriding.

$$U_T(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C) | U_N(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C)$$

$$HB = 1000 > HB = 700$$

$$R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм} < R_a = 1,6 \text{ мкм}$$

$$\sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ МПа} > \sigma_0 = 800 \text{ МПа}$$

x - degree of applicability

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{700 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,6} + \frac{800 \cdot 1}{1000} = \frac{0,7 + 0,39 + 0,8}{3} = \frac{1,89}{3} = 0,63 \quad (6)$$

As a result of the study, the degree of applicability of nitrification in relation to the required properties $x = 0,63$ formed

Cementation.

$$U_T(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C) | U_C(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C)$$

$$HB = 1000 > HB = 560$$

$$R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм} < R_a = 1,6 \text{ мкм}$$

$$\sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ МПа} > \sigma_0 = 900 \text{ МПа}$$

x - level of applicability

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{560 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,6} + \frac{900 \cdot 1}{1000} = \frac{0,56 + 0,39 + 0,9}{3} = \frac{1,85}{3} = 0,61 \quad (7)$$

The degree of applicability of cementation to the required properties as a result of the study $x = 0,61$ formed

Chrome plating.

$$U_T(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C) | U_{Cr}(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C)$$

$$HB = 1000 < HB = 1100$$

$$R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм} = R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм}$$

$$\sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ МПа} = \sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ МПа}$$

x - degree of applicability

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{\frac{1100 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} + \frac{1000 \cdot 1}{1000}}{3} = \frac{1,1 + 0,5 + 1}{3} = \frac{2,6}{3} = 0,86 \quad (8)$$

As a result of the study, the applicability level of chrome plating with respect to the required properties $x = 0,86$ formed

Cementite coating. In order to comprehensively use the properties of cementite, we will change the composition of the coating in different percentages and analyze the results obtained from the coating.[5]

Experiment 1. Cementite

$$U_T(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C) | U_{Co}(HB, R_a, \sigma_0, C)$$

$$HB = 1000 < HB = 1050$$

$$R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм} = R_a = 1,25 \text{ мкм}$$

$$\sigma_0 = 1000 \text{ МПа} < \sigma_0 = 1010 \text{ МПа}$$

x - degree of applicability

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{\frac{1050 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} + \frac{1010 \cdot 1}{1000}}{3} = \frac{1,05 + 0,5 + 1,01}{3} = \frac{2,56}{3} = 0,85 \quad (9)$$

As a result of the study, the level of applicability of cementite coating in relation to the required properties $x = 0,85$ was .

Experiment 2. Cementite coating:

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{\frac{1137 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} + \frac{1031 \cdot 1}{1000}}{3} = \frac{1,14 + 0,5 + 1,03}{3} = \frac{2,67}{3} = 0,89 \quad (10)$$

As a result of the study, the degree of applicability of Cementite coating in relation to the required properties $x = 0,89$ formed

Experiment 3. Cementite (70) coating:

$$x = \frac{U_N(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)}{U_T(HB \cdot k, R_a \cdot k, \sigma_0 \cdot k)} = \frac{\frac{1225 \cdot 1}{1000} + \frac{1,25 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} + \frac{1052 \cdot 1}{1000}}{3} = \frac{1,23 + 0,5 + 1,05}{3} = \frac{2,78}{3} = 0,92 \quad (11)$$

As a result of the study, the degree of applicability of Cementite coating in relation to the required properties $x = 0,92$ formed.

Table 2.

Process name	nitrification	Cementation	Chrome plating	Cementite coating
Level of coverage	0.63	0.61	0.86	0.85 (80/20) 0.89 (75/25) 0.92 (70/30)

Galvanic layerless coated samples are also interesting. Theirs on the surfaces chrome cover in general harvest not even poor quality hardness though indicators consecutively roller with in comparison sharp decreases. of this event only one explanation have: reaction in the bath to a temperature of 55 °C temperature of 55°C when heated rising up to go if the quality of the coating and of the stamp surface roughness Demand done to quality answer does not give.[4]

Conclusion

It turned out that one of the most suitable chemical methods for increasing the service life of stamps is cementation, this method has the advantage of low cost, surface cleanliness, hardness and strength at the required level.

References

1. Grigoryev S.I., Ilichev L.L., Rudakov V.I. Ionno-plazmennoye uprochneniye instrumentalnykh staley. Uchebnoye posobiye.-Orenburg:GOUOGU,2005.-41 5s.
2. Gorbachev S.V. Vliyaniye temperatury na gidroliz kak kineticheskiy metod issledovaniya prirody elektroximicheskix processov // V kn.: Trudy IV soveshaniya po elektroximii.-M.:ANSSSR,1959,-S. 61-71.
3. Guryev A.M. Vysokoeffektivnaya texnologiya diffuzionnogo uprochneniya shtampovogo instrumenta [Tekst] /A. M. Guryev, A. N. Jdanov, L. G. Voroshnin // Tez. dokl. Mejdunarodnoy nauchno-texnicheskoy Rossiysko-Germanskoy konferensii «Plasticheskaya i termicheskaya obrabotka sovremennykh metallicheskih materialov» 17 – 19 maya 1995g. – Sankt-Peterburg.1995. – S. 109.
4. Damaskin B.B. Praktikum po prikladnoy elektroximii: Uchebnoye posobiye dlya xim. Spes. Vuzov / B.B. Damaskin, O.A. Petriy, B.I. Nodlovchenko i dr.; podredaksiyey B.B. Damaskina.-M.:Vyssh.shk., 1991.-228s.
5. Zavolokin O.A. Razrabotka mexaniko-ximiko-termicheskoy obrabotki detaley pri uprochnenii borirovaniyem v obmazkax TVCH - nagrevom / Diss. kand. texn. nauk. - Kursk, 2007. - 194 s